

This is a pre-publication version of the following article:

Motschenbacher, Heiko. 2019. "Methods in language, gender and sexuality studies: An overview." *Wiener Slawistischer Almanach* 84: 43-70.

When citing from or referring to this article, please use the final publisher version.

This article documents work carried out within the LIDISNO (Linguistic Dimensions of Sexual Normativity) Project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 740257.

Marie Skłodowska-Curie
Actions

Methods in Language, Gender and Sexuality Studies: An Overview

Heiko Motschenbacher

Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Bergen

heim@hvl.no

1. Introduction

Language, gender and sexuality (LGS) studies have developed into a vast and internally heterogeneous field that draws on a broad range of linguistic methods (see the contributions in the collection on language and gender methodologies edited by Harrington, Litosseliti, Sauntson & Sunderland 2008, and Motschenbacher 2012a or Zimman & Hall 2016 for bibliographical overviews). This article presents an overview of these methodologies. Based on an outline of major theoretical strands in LGS research (feminist linguistics, lavender linguistics, discursive gender linguistics and queer linguistics), the methodological overview discusses common approaches in three areas: gender- and sexuality-related structural linguistics, sociolinguistics and discursive linguistics. Even though an attempt is made to cover the field in its entire breadth, the discussion centres on queer linguistics as the most recent strand of work in LGS studies. The critical reflexivity in terms of method selection that contemporary research on LGS necessitates is further illustrated by a discussion of the methodological challenges of corpus linguistics for queer linguistic inquiry.

2. Theoretical strands in language, gender and sexuality studies

LGS has developed into an internally diverse research area that is united by an interest in how language and linguistic practices contribute to the production of gender and sexuality (and potentially further aspects that intersect with these two dimensions). However, such work may operate from various, and sometimes even incompatible, perspectives on the relationship between language, gender and sexuality, which are associated with various political stances: Is it the researcher's goal to empower women and to make them visible? To empower LGBT people and to put them on the linguistic map? Or maybe to challenge dominant gender- and sexuality-related categories and discourses? The answers

to these questions are likely to shape a researcher’s way of approaching a certain topic or research object. In other words, theoretical considerations will invariably inform decisions about which methods are chosen, and they will influence how these methods are applied to serve certain research purposes. Therefore, it is necessary to give a brief overview of theoretical strands in this research field.

Table 1 provides an (admittedly simplified) overview of central strands in LGS research. The neat categorisation suggested by the firm dividing lines between the boxes in the table is artificial, because, in reality, one finds substantial overlap and cross-fertilisation between the four major strands identified. Broken lines would therefore be a more adequate representation. Note that this classification is a purely descriptive one. Individual researchers may not explicitly position their work as belonging to one of the four categories. This is partly due to the fact that some research of relevance to the field of LGS refrains from contributing to or advancing theoretical debates. For example, experimental sociophonetic work that seeks to detect differences between female and male, or between heterosexual and gay or lesbian subjects, and does not engage in a critical discussion of such differences, can easily be placed within difference-based feminist and lavender linguistics, even though the respective researchers themselves are unlikely to practice such an explicit theoretical positioning. Still, the classification constitutes a valid instrument for illuminating basic theoretical strands on which concrete studies are (explicitly or implicitly) based.

	Language and gender	Language and sexuality
Focus on dominance / difference	<p>Feminist linguistics</p> <p><i>Main research goals:</i> making women linguistically visible exposing male linguistic dominance showing how women and men use language differently revealing how women and men are represented differently in language</p>	<p>Lavender linguistics</p> <p><i>Main research goals:</i> making LGBT people linguistically visible exposing heterosexual linguistic dominance showing how LGBT subjects use language revealing how LGBT subjects are represented in language</p>
Focus on discourse	<p>Discursive gender linguistics</p> <p><i>Main research goals:</i> showing how gender is discursively shaped</p>	<p>Queer linguistics</p> <p><i>Main research goals:</i> showing how gender and sexuality are discursively shaped</p>

	questioning gender-related categories and binarisms exposing normative gender mechanisms documenting less traditional gender performances	questioning gender- and sexuality-related categories and binarisms exposing normative gender and sexual mechanisms documenting non-normative gender and sexuality performances
--	---	--

Table 1: Overview of central strands in language, gender and sexuality studies

Table 1 distinguishes four major strands by taking their thematic focal points (gender vs. sexuality) and theoretical foundations into account. It needs to be stressed that more traditional approaches have not been replaced by more recent ones. Rather, they co-exist with them today, with a tendency for the more recent approaches to prevail.

Feminist linguistics (since the 1970s; e.g. Cameron 1985, Coates & Cameron 1988, Lakoff 1975, Mills 2012, Winter & Pauwels 2006) and lavender linguistics (since the 1990s; Kulick 1999, 2000, Leap 1995, 2002, Thurlow 2001) mark the starting points of language and gender and language and sexuality studies respectively. Central research goals of feminist linguistics are making women linguistically visible, exposing male dominance (sexism), and showing how women differ from men in their language behaviour and in the way they are represented in language. Lavender linguistics has traditionally focused on making the language-related experiences of LGBT people visible, exposing heterosexual dominance (homophobia, heterosexism), and documenting how LGBT subjects use language and are represented in language in different ways to heterosexual people.

Butler's (1990) highly influential work on gender as performative, and on the production and naturalisation of the heterosexual matrix has had a clear impact on the field. This has resulted in the addition of discursively oriented work to the field of LGS (see also Baker 2013 for corpus linguistic evidence of this academic shift). This has also brought gender- and sexuality-related linguistic fields closer together, with discursive gender linguistics focusing somewhat more on the discursive production of gender (e.g. Baker 2016, Bucholtz 2003, Kiesling 2005, Sunderland 2004, Sunderland & Litosseliti 2002), and queer linguistics concentrating more on the discursive production of sexuality (Barrett 2002, Hall 2013, Leap 2015, Motschenbacher 2010, 2011). The central research goals of these more recent strands include showing how gender and sexuality are discursively shaped, questioning gender- and sexuality-related binarisms and categories, exposing normative mechanisms in the

discursive production of gender and sexuality, and documenting less traditional and non-normative linguistic performances of gender and sexuality.

3. Methodological Overview

The linguistic inquiry into LGS has concentrated on three aspects: linguistic structures (the linguistic material we use to convey gender- and sexuality-related messages), the linguistic behaviour of gendered or sexually defined social groups (language use in relation to the language user), and the discursive construction of gender and sexuality via linguistic practices (language use as a manifestation of discursive effects). These aspects require slightly different methodologies, and are discussed below as the subject matter of three linguistic subfields: structural linguistics (Section 3.1), sociolinguistics (Section 3.2), and discursive linguistics (Section 3.3). The references in Sections 3.1 to 3.3 provide examples of studies that have used a certain methodological approach.

3.1 Structural linguistics

The first area covered by LGS research is the relevance of gender and sexuality in linguistic structures of various kinds (see Motschenbacher 2015 on structural gender linguistics). The research object in this area is how the language system (morphology, syntax, lexis, and semantics) is put to use to represent people as gendered, ungendered, sexualized or sexually identified. Structural analyses have been part and parcel of language and gender research from its very beginnings in the 1970s, with studies focusing, for example, on female linguistic invisibility as found in male and masculine generic forms (e.g. Paterson 2014), semantic and distributional asymmetries between female/feminine and male/masculine personal reference forms (e.g. Kochman-Haladyj & Kleparski 2011), and gendered asymmetries in grammatical phenomena like agreement (e.g. Braun & Haig 2010) or word order in binomials (e.g. Motschenbacher 2013). Further aspects that are commonly studied in structural gender linguistics include personal nouns, pronouns, personal names, word-formation, gendered phraseological units, lexical gender, social gender, grammatical gender and referential gender (Hellinger & Bußmann 2001, Motschenbacher 2015, Motschenbacher & Weikert 2015).

Sexuality has a less central and less direct impact on language structures than gender. Relevant aspects include the investigation of the means that a language provides for talking or writing about sexual identities (personal nouns, adjectival labels; e.g. Coleman-Fountain 2014, Nevala & Hintikka 2009),

relationships (romantic partner nouns, marriage-related vocabulary; e.g. Harvey 1997, Jones, Mills, Paterson, Turner & Coffey-Glover 2017), desires (body-part lexis, adjectives of physical beauty; e.g. Braun & Kitzinger 2001, Makoni 2016) and sexual practices (verbs of lovemaking and their grammatical constructions, which tell us something about the agency of the social actors involved; e.g. Clark 1992, Manning 1997).

Traditionally, feminist linguists used introspection to discuss various forms of the linguistic discrimination of women (see Lakoff 1975). These initial discussions had the merit of putting gender on the linguistic map and were subsequently backed up by various methods that could document these issues empirically. Today, gender- and sexuality-related language structures are studied in a range of different ways and at various linguistic levels. Morphological studies on gender representation typically concentrate on derivation and compounding as the main means of creating female (and sometimes male) personal nouns (e.g. Khan & Daneman 2011, Kornexl 2008, Peitsara 2006), or on the morphological means to mark grammatical gender (e.g. Doleschal 2015, Morin 2010). Syntactic studies have generally focused on issues such as gender agreement (e.g. Scheller-Boltz 2017), pronominalisation (e.g. Gardelle 2015) or word order in coordinative structures (e.g. Motschenbacher 2013). Gender- and sexuality-related vocabulary has been covered by lexicographical work (e.g. Baker 2002, Cage 2003, Mills 1989) and studies on linguistic gender bias in dictionaries (e.g. Connor Martin 2005, George 1999, Hidalgo Tenorio 2000). Lexicological and lexicosemantic work has investigated the lexical fields of female or male personal nouns (e.g. Kleparski 2004, Persson & Rydén 1996) and other gender- or sexuality-associated lexical fields (e.g. Norri 1996, Tissari 2005).

Scholars conducting semantic studies of LGS may operate from two major perspectives. Researchers adopting the semasiological perspective investigate the meaning potential of linguistic structures. Evidence for connotational meanings and semantic prosodies can, for example, be found in the collocates of a form in a text corpus. At the same time, there is a large body of experimental, psycholinguistic work that uses questionnaires or perception tests to find out how subjects interpret certain linguistic forms (e.g. Khan & Daneman 2011, Miller & James 2009). By contrast, research adopting the onomasiological perspective takes a certain concept as a starting point and sets out to identify the linguistic structures by which it can be expressed (e.g. Persson & Rydén 1995).

In areas where the linguistic means are deemed insufficient, suggesting new forms may be pertinent (for example, more inclusive pronouns and personal nouns). This is especially common in more radical branches of feminist and queer linguistics (e.g. Baumgartinger 2008, Musgrave 1992) and may clash with

application-oriented work. Sometimes existing linguistic material is used in novel ways, thus causing a broadening or shift in its meaning potential (e.g. singular *they*). The creation of neologisms and the intentional promotion of meaning shifts are central strategies of gender- and sexuality-related language policies (see also Motschenbacher 2014a, Pauwels 2011).

Another important method for the description of gender- and sexuality-related linguistic structures is the comparison of languages, as found in contrastive linguistics (cf. König & Gast 2009) and language typology (cf. Velupillai 2012; see Hellinger & Bussmann 2001-2003, Hellinger & Motschenbacher 2015). Various types of comparison are conceivable, ranging from the detailed comparison of two languages as to gender and sexual representation (contrastive linguistic endpole; e.g. Jaworski 1986, Jung 1997, Kremer 1997) to a comparison of many languages with respect to a particular feature relevant to the expression of gender and sexuality (language typological endpole; e.g. Corbett 2005, 2014, Siewierska 2005). The contrastive linguistic dimension can also be applied historically, that is, in the shape of comparisons of linguistic structures across various developmental stages of a language or variety. Such procedures help illuminate grammatical and semantic developments in gender- and sexuality-related linguistic structures (e.g. Bammesberger & Grzega 2001, Frank 2003).

From a queer linguistic perspective, comparisons across varieties and historical language stages are a pertinent way of documenting the cultural and historical linguistic relativity of gender and sexuality. In other words, such studies provide valuable evidence for the fact that gender and sexuality are not (purely) natural or biological, but are shaped culturally and socially. This perspective shifts structural linguistic analyses closer to discursive linguistic analyses (see Section 3.3), that is, the language system and language structures can be viewed as harbouring highly entrenched gender- and sexuality-related discourses that language users draw on across many usage contexts.

A methodology that can be used to arrive at a more usage-based picture of the meaning potential, collocations, syntactic constructions and occurrence frequency of a given linguistic structure is corpus linguistics (e.g. Baker 2010, Motschenbacher 2018b, forthcoming c). This method is discussed in more detail in Section 4.

3.2 Sociolinguistics

Another field that has focused on LGS since the 1970s is sociolinguistics. Studies in this area investigate the linguistic behaviour of individuals or social groups whose identification is reliant on gender and/or sexuality. Contrary to the previous research area, the focus is here not on the language system but on actual language use, viewed in relation to the language user.

A cornerstone of a great deal of sociolinguistic work is the collection of naturally occurring language data. Ideally, researchers would want to work with data that reflects language users' "normal" behaviour, that is, behaviour they would show in the same way if they were not being observed for research purposes. However, as surreptitious recording and data use without subjects' informed consent is deemed unethical today, researchers need to find ways of data collection that do not compromise data quality too much. Subjects can, for example, be asked to give their informed consent on data collection, analysis, storage and publication after their language use has been recorded, or, if informed consent is obtained in advance, the analysis may concentrate on later phases of the data collection process, to make sure that subjects have undergone a certain routinisation with being recorded/observed.

The methods that can be used for sociolinguistic investigations range from methods that work in a highly contextualised fashion to methods that investigate language behaviour of social groups more generally. Contextualised approaches include conversation analysis, membership categorisation analysis, positioning analysis, linguistic ethnography, and pragmatic analysis. These can be carried out using naturally occurring language data or language data that has been elicited in sociolinguistic interviews or focus group discussions (e.g. Litosseliti 2003).

Conversation analysis (CA) is a strictly local approach to the analysis of conversational language use. Interactional data are typically recorded, closely transcribed (e.g. Jefferson 2004, Kitzinger 2008, Liddicoat 2007) and then analysed in terms of the interactional work that participants engage in (e.g. turn-taking, overlaps, floor apportionment, minimal responses, topic initiation, mitigation of dispreferred responses). Early feminist-inspired research in this area regularly documented the dominant interactional behaviour of men in mixed-sex conversations (e.g. Fishman 1978). Yet, apart from this mechanism of gender-related dominance, many other mechanisms have been shown to be relevant for the interactional performance of gender (Speer 2005, Speer & Stokoe 2011, Stokoe 2008, Wilkinson & Kitzinger 2014) and sexuality (Heisterkamp 2016, Kitzinger 2005, Land & Kitzinger 2005, Turowetz & Hollander 2012).

A central tenet of CA is that aspects that are treated as relevant in the analysis must also have been made relevant by interactants in the data. This means that, even when a conversation takes place among lesbian women exclusively for example, gender and sexuality cannot automatically be claimed to be relevant if the women do not make these aspects relevant in their talk. At the same time, work in CA has shown that even the use of lexically gendered forms (like *woman* or *husband*) does not automatically make gender relevant (see Kitzinger 2007, Kitzinger & Wilkinson 2017) and that lexically gender-neutral forms can be used in ways that make gender relevant (see Stockill & Kitzinger 2007). A related approach to the analysis of conversational data is membership categorisation analysis (e.g. Hall, Gough, Seymour-Smith & Hansen 2012, Sokalska-Bennett 2017, Stokoe 2010, 2012), which focuses less on structural features of conversations and more on the interactional negotiation of identity categories.

There is a lot of queer linguistic potential in CA and membership categorisation analysis, since these approaches can challenge the automatic relevance of identity categories and may highlight contexts in which gender and/or sexuality are irrelevant to communication. Moreover, these approaches can easily show how gender and sexual categories are negotiated and performed in locally diverse ways. One aspect for which CA has sometimes been criticised is its (supposed) blindness to larger power structures that extend beyond individual conversations and systematically lead to the oppression, discrimination, stigmatisation or exclusion of certain gender or sexual groups (see discussion in Kitzinger 2000). Such criticism has been voiced especially by scholars in the critical discourse analysis tradition (see further below), and has induced some researchers to suggest composite approaches uniting aspects of both approaches in the analysis of gender and sexuality (such as positioning analysis; Korobov 2001, 2013, Wetherell 1998).

Pragmatics is another wide field of inquiry in which investigations of linguistic practices are analysed in relation to usage context. It is the communicative function of utterances and their linguistic features in a given context that is of interest here. Pragmatic phenomena are often analysed in relation to the gender of the language users, thus adding a distinctly sociolinguistic dimension to the analysis (see Cameron 1998a, 2005). Pragmatic aspects that have been related to gender (often with an additional focus on cultural differences) include various speech act types (e.g. Harting 2005, Ogiermann 2008, Wolfson 1984, Motschenbacher 2017) or (im)politeness phenomena (e.g. Chalupnik, Christie & Mullany 2017, Holmes 1995, Mills 2003).

Various dimensions of sexuality have also been explored using pragmatic analyses (e.g. Chirrey 2003, Harvey 2002, Johnson 2018, Kuhn 1999, McGowan 2009, Watson 2012). Pragmatic methods can be fruitfully incorporated in queer linguistic work if they do not (just) involve a mere mapping of linguistic behaviour onto monolithic gender and sexual categories, but if they provide space for a more nuanced understanding of gender and sexuality that is able to question such categories through demonstrating their internal diversity and overlap.

Another type of inquiry that takes the local usage context into account is linguistic ethnography. In this approach, language use is analysed to shed light on the routinised communicative behaviours of a community of practice (Eckert & McConnell-Ginet 1992). Data collection here usually requires researchers to become participant-observers or, ideally, community members – a position that enables them to incorporate insider knowledge into their analyses. Observational data in the shape of ethnographic notes and community-relevant text documents are often supplemented by interviews with community members. In certain communities of practice, gender and/or sexuality can be shown to play a substantial role not just in the social configuration of the community but also in the communicative practices that community members treat as normal (see, for example, Bucholtz 1999, Ehrlich 1999, Holmes & Meyerhoff 1999, Ostermann 2003 on gender, and Jones 2012, 2014, Luchjenbroers & Aldridge-Waddon 2011, Schneider 2013a, 2013b, Takahashi 2013 on sexuality).

Importantly for queer linguistic research purposes, communities of practice typically possess both central and peripheral members, with the latter usually showing less typical communicative behaviour for the community as a whole. In other words, the concept of a community of practice allows the researcher to deal with subjects who exhibit less normative, even community-atypical behaviours. At the same time, the idea of a community of practice is based on the notion of doing something together and is thus an adequate means to eschew, or weaken the influence of, monolithic identity categories. This may prove especially useful for language and sexuality research that focuses more on the communicative performance of desire or sexual practices rather than sexual identities.

On the less locally contextualised side, there is a long tradition of variationist sociolinguistic studies providing quantitative evidence for systematic variation in language use in relation to certain identity categories (such as social class or ethnicity). Many such study designs also quantify the use of linguistic features in relation to gender, often finding that, within a certain social class, ethnic group or community of practice, female speakers use more standard variants and tend to lead language change (e.g. Trudgill 1972, Eckert 1989,

Labov 1990). A lot of this variationist work is generally not conceptualised as being part of the field of LGS, even though its findings are potentially relevant for this field. Due to its reliance on quantification in relation to fixed (often binary) gender categories, the relationship between such variationist work and recent work in LGS has become problematic (see, however, Holmes-Elliott 2016, Hultgren 2008, Lawson 2011, Levon 2011 for more recent work). A related field of investigation that also has more bearing on the analysis of sexuality is sociophonetics (Cameron 2011, Podesva & Kajino 2014). The phonetic analysis of female, male, heterosexual, gay, lesbian and trans-identified people's voices as well as phonetic perception studies in relation to these social groups form a vibrant field of inquiry today (see Munson, Ryherd & Kemper 2017, Russell 2017, Zimman 2013, and contributions in Podesva & Eckert 2011).

The major merit of variationist work for queer linguistics is probably that it can document intersectionality effects that question a monolithic handling of female and male as two fixed, mutually incompatible categories. Intra-categorical diversity, rather than inter-categorical difference, thus turns out to be a crucial perspective on variationist data. The question of whether monolithic female and male "genderlects" (female- and male-specific language varieties) exist is today generally answered in the negative. However, genderlectal features may play a role in contexts where femininity and masculinity are constructed via linguistic behaviour in stereotypical ways (such as in advertising; see Motschenbacher 2007).

Gender-based variation in grammatical and lexical features has also, to some extent, been studied using corpus linguistic methods (see Section 4 for a more detailed discussion). Again, it is the reliance on binary gender categories often witnessed in such studies that represents a major problem, especially for queer linguistic inquiry (see Motschenbacher 2018b). Most of this work has drawn on major English reference corpora (e.g. Grimm 2008, Rayson, Leech & Hodges 1997, Schmid 2003, 2015). Sexuality-related sociolinguistic corpus-based work is rare due to the scarcity of language corpora that have been annotated for speakers' sexual identifications (but see King 2011).

In applied linguistics, investigations of differences between female and male language learners' linguistic output has often informed scholarly work on first and second language acquisition (e.g. Gleason & Ely 2002, Jiménez Catalán 2010, Lange, Euler & Zaretsky 2016).

3.3 Discursive linguistics

In the field of discursive linguistics, the focus is on language use (like in sociolinguistics), but viewed in relation to the discursive effects it has, rather than in relation to the language user. In other words, researchers in this area are more interested in how ways of seeing the world (Foucauldian “discourses”) are over-individually and intertextually produced and upheld through linguistic practices, beyond the boundaries of particular language users or social groups.

In LGS studies, central discourses that have been studied are those associated with various femininities (e.g. Conradie 2011), masculinities (e.g. Baker & Levon 2015), trans-identities (e.g. Baker 2014), sexism (e.g. Lillian 2007), feminism (e.g. Jaworska & Krishnamurthy 2012), gender binarism (e.g. Zimman 2014), gender dominance (e.g. Adams, Towns & Gavey 1995), gender difference (e.g. Pidwell 1998), heterosexuality (e.g. Motschenbacher 2012b), gay male sexualities (e.g. Baker 2005), lesbian sexualities (e.g. Koller 2011), homophobia (e.g. Peterson 2011), heterosexism (e.g. Sandfield & Percy 2003), heteronormativity (e.g. Bogetic 2010), homonormativity and other sexual normativities (Motschenbacher 2014b, forthcoming a), rape and sexual consent (e.g. Ehrlich 2001), and heterosexual and same-sex marriage (e.g. Bachmann 2011, Jäkel 2014). The work in this area loosely clusters around various types of discourse analysis, with critical discourse analysis being a central orientation point. While we find a predominance of individualised spoken data in sociolinguistic work on LGS, LGS-related discursive linguistics typically (though not exclusively) concentrates on (written) public language use in textual genres that potentially have a wider impact on society in terms of reception. The critical dimension of most of this work goes hand in hand with certain political stances and a motivation to induce social change through research that exposes harmful gender- and sexuality-related discourses and their consequences.

In discursive linguistic studies, linguistic features are viewed as potential traces of discourses, that is, they contribute, together with other means of making meaning, to the way the world is conceptualised. Moreover, they are treated as a matter of motivated choice, where the basic assumption is that there are reasons why language users say or write something in a certain way and do not draw on alternative linguistic material that is likely to convey other messages. The degree of power associated with certain discourses ranges from highly naturalised, dominant worldviews and ideologies to more marginalised or even silenced discourses, which are drawn on by a minority of language users or which cannot usually be overtly expressed. Needless to say, queer linguistics has a strong interest in both exposing harmful dominant gender- and sexuality-related

discourses and documenting marginalised and silenced discourses that challenge the notion that the former are natural. While an analysis of dominant discourses can normally draw on numerous, easily identifiable examples from a dataset, the analysis of less frequently surfacing discourses represents a challenge for discourse analysts and has only recently received greater methodological attention (see Kulick 2005 and contributions in Schröter & Taylor 2018). Another consideration that is of particular relevance for queer linguistics is that research on LGS should ideally not focus on binary differences (female-male, hetero-homo, gay-lesbian) exclusively in its study design, but also consider linguistic similarities and overlaps (see Taylor 2013).

Critical discourse studies have developed into a wide and internally heterogeneous field whose various schools draw on partly different theoretical and methodological premises (see contributions in Wodak & Meyer 2016) and are open to interdisciplinary influences. Individual schools vary, for example, in the degree of attention they pay to linguistic details in their analyses. Which linguistic features are studied depends crucially on the type of discourse that is being investigated. Various areas are potentially relevant in this respect, including grammatical, lexical, semantic, pragmatic, and rhetorical features (see Machin & Mayr 2012 for a discussion of features commonly analysed in CDA studies). For LGS studies more specifically, linguistic features that are involved in the discursive construction of people as gendered or ungendered (pronouns, personal nouns, personal names), or of sexual identities (sexual descriptive adjectives and personal nouns), sexual relationships, desires and sexual practices (compare gender and sexuality-related structures discussed in Section 3.1) are often important reference points for linguistic analysis.

Discursive linguistic approaches that have been used in LGS research besides critical discourse analysis (Koller 2011, Leap 2015, Motschenbacher 2018c, Motschenbacher & Stegu 2013) include feminist critical discourse analysis (Lazar 2018, Wodak 2008), multimodal analysis (Hiramoto & Teo 2015, Machin, Caldas-Coulthard & Milani 2016, Milani 2013, Sunderland & McGlashan 2012), poststructuralist discourse analysis (Baxter 2003, Naseem 2006), appraisal analysis (Page 2003, Sauntson 2007, 2015), systemic functional linguistics (Koller 2015, Yang 2017), and discursive psychology (Edley & Wetherell 2008, Speer & Potter 2002). A methodology that has become increasingly popular in gender- and sexuality-related discursive studies is corpus linguistics (see Motschenbacher 2018b for an overview of studies and contributions in Motschenbacher 2018a for recent examples of such work). This methodology is discussed in more detail in relation to its applicability in queer linguistics in Section 4.

While discursive linguistic approaches have commonly been used to study the relationship between language and gender/sexuality in public contexts such as media (e.g. Hunt 2015) and politics (e.g. Wodak 2005), another central domain that has been subject to such discursive analyses is education and, in particular, foreign language education. A central issue in such work is the representation of gender and sexuality in educational contexts, with increasing inclusivity being a major concern (e.g. Carr & Pauwels 2006, Decke-Cornill & Volkman 2007, Motschenbacher 2016a). Aspects studied include classroom interactions (e.g. Baxter 2002, Sauntson 2012), teaching materials (e.g. Motschenbacher forthcoming b, Sunderland 2015), or educational policy documents (Sauntson & Simpson 2011, Sauntson & Sundaram 2016).

3.4 Mixed methods

Even though the outline in Sections 3.1 to 3.3 suggests that the three fields are clearly distinct, it needs to be noted that such a representation is to some extent artificial, as actual studies on LGS often draw on aspects from more than one category and combine them. This is often done to let the various approaches mutually relativise each other in a process of methodological (and sometimes theoretical) triangulation. But even within the individual approaches, one tends to find methodological pluralism. Critical discourse analysis, for example, generally adopts eclectic research procedures that allow researchers to combine various methods in an interdisciplinary fashion. Similarly, a great deal of work in LGS studies combines quantitative and qualitative forms of analysis, with corpus linguistics being a case in point. Apart from this, some of the approaches discussed have been in extended dialogue with each other, and this dialogue has also informed LGS research. For example, there have been efforts to combine conversation analysis and critical discourse analysis (Weatherall, Stubbe, Sunderland, Baxter 2008), qualitative critical discourse analysis and quantitative corpus linguistics (Baker & Levon 2015), structural gender linguistics and poststructuralist discourse analysis (Motschenbacher 2016b), or corpus linguistics and psycholinguistics (Motschenbacher & Roivainen forthcoming).

4. Corpus linguistic methods in queer linguistics

This section illustrates how the theoretical underpinnings of LGS research have an influence not just on which linguistic methods are chosen, but also on the

question of how these methods should be employed in accordance with theoretically informed research goals. The discussion concentrates on the use of corpus linguistic methods in queer linguistic work.

In contrast to the other types of discursive linguistic approaches, which tend to show a strong concentration on detailed qualitative analyses of language data, corpus linguistics constitutes a primarily quantitative type of analysis that can be supplemented by qualitative analyses. The application of corpus linguistics in queer linguistics is an undertaking that needs some critical reflection. Queer theoretical issues like the questioning of gender- and sexuality-related binarisms and categories (e.g. Bing & Bergvall 1996, contributions in Zimman, Davis & Raclaw 2014) or the foregrounding of non-normative aspects to weaken traditional, dominant discourses have been incorporated in much of the qualitative discourse analytic or ethnographic work on language and sexuality. In (mainly) quantitative approaches such as corpus linguistics, their implementation appears to be more complex. Below I discuss five aspects of corpus linguistics that pose particular challenges to queer linguistics: quantification, reliance on form, concentration on frequent features, categorisation, and difference focus.

Corpus linguistics is primarily quantitative in the sense that the quantification of the occurrence of linguistic features plays a central role. An advantage of this is that larger amounts of data can be incorporated, which facilitates a more comprehensive analysis than in a purely qualitative study design (which will normally concentrate on the detailed analysis of selected data extracts). The quantitative findings are generally submitted to statistical significance tests, which are often perceived as being associated with a higher level of objectivity. However, queer linguistics takes a more nuanced stance on statistical significance testing, viewing it as only one of many instruments that can be used to arrive at empirically valid findings and that is, therefore, generally used in triangulation with other, qualitative methods (such as an analysis of concordance lines).

Some studies approach corpora in a bottom-up fashion (an approach often called “corpus-driven”). But LGS researchers normally conduct their studies with certain aims or theoretical issues in mind that will inform their choice of data, tools, tool settings, analytical categories, and interpretive strategies. Their critical focus on the production of ideologies surfacing in the discursive construction of gender and sexuality, and on associated normativities, discrimination, exclusion, stigmatisation and marginalisation, will usually lead them to adopt a problem-oriented corpus-based, rather than corpus-driven, approach (see also McEnery & Hardie 2012: 5–6).

Since quantification generally serves as the entry point for corpus linguistic analyses, it is self-evident that high-frequency items are more likely to attract the researcher's attention, that is, what will be selected for further qualitative inspection will usually be something that has been proven to occur relatively frequently in a given corpus. Low-frequency items tend to be ignored, even though they may contribute cumulatively to a certain discursive effect or may represent traces of alternative, non-normative discourses. This eradication of marginal linguistic phenomena is potentially a problem in queer linguistics (see Baker & Egbert 2016: 195), which, in its deliberate attempt to adopt the perspective of the marginalised or peripheral, has an interest not just in majority but also minority patterns (see also Barrett 2014: 219). In queer linguistic corpus investigations, there should, therefore be some space for the identification of less frequently or infrequently occurring features, which may be useful for highlighting alternative or silenced discourses, or for challenging dominant discursive regimes (see, however, Motschenbacher 2018b on the problematic relationship between frequency of occurrence and the degree to which certain discourses are entrenched).

A related concern about corpus linguistics from a queer linguistic perspective is that corpus searches necessarily rely on form, formal identity, and formal presence in corpora. This fixation on linguistic form may be problematic where functional variability, contextual meaning or semantic change play a role – aspects that often receive greater attention in poststructuralist approaches such as queer linguistics and that cannot be fully retrieved by exclusively formally based search queries. The fact that harmful gender- and sexuality-related discourses such as sexism, heteronormativity, heterosexism, and homophobia tend to surface in more subtle and less explicit ways today than in former times (see Love & Baker 2015, Mills 2008), therefore, poses new challenges for the investigation of these discourses with corpus linguistic tools.

The necessity of relying on linguistic forms also means that corpus linguistics can, by default, only analyse aspects that are formally present in a corpus, while formal absences and the question of which forms could potentially have been used, but (maybe for strategic reasons) were not, are notoriously difficult to tackle with the use of corpus tools. However, the “importance of what gets left out” (Kulick 2005) has long been recognised in critical discourse studies and queer linguistics (see also Love & Baker 2015, Partington 2014, Schröter & Taylor 2018). For example, certain grammatical constructions or lexical combinations that are possible in principle but occur only infrequently or not at all in a data set may instantiate discourses that are perceived to be marked or non-normative. Co-occurrence analysis is a corpus linguistic method that can be employed to make more detailed statements about these formal absences and

infrequent usage types, by analysing the occurrence of specific word combinations as central components of a larger semantic or conceptual field (see Motschenbacher forthcoming c).

Furthermore, as a quantitative methodology, corpus linguistics is strongly category-based. It employs such categories as language user groups, text genres, lemmas, parts of speech, semantic categories or other categories for which a corpus has been annotated to make sense of the data. However, categories are typically problematised in queer theory-informed research (see Barrett 2014 for a queer linguistic critique of the discursive regimes governing formal linguistics), as they rest on the notion of intra-categorical homogeneity and thus cover up effects of intra-categorical heterogeneity, prototypicality, normativity, and problematic category members, precisely the phenomena that are of interest to queer linguists.

Even though category scepticism in queer-minded work potentially targets all categories, it is often socially relevant categories that form the centre of attention. In language and sexuality studies, gender- and sexuality-related binarisms (male – female; masculine – feminine; heterosexual – homosexual; gay – lesbian etc.; cf. Bing & Bergvall 1996) are the categories that have been scrutinised most intensively, as they do not just facilitate harmful simplistic perceptions (such as “good vs. bad”, or “primary vs. secondary”) but also tend to support the marginalisation and stigmatisation of aspects that do not neatly fit into a binary scheme (i.e., a scheme that normatively dictates opposition and incompatibility). In corpus linguistics, however, quantification is often based on the very binarisms that are supposed to be challenged from a queer linguistic point of view. To address this problem, corpus linguists in LGS studies have to find ways to question categories, despite the fact that their research builds on them. This can be achieved through a secondary qualitative analysis that highlights problematic category members and contextual meaning negotiation. Diachronic and cross-linguistic corpus analyses also help foster an understanding of the historical and cultural specificity of categories that is in tune with queer linguistic tenets.

A final area of concern is the concentration on differences between corpora, to the detriment of the documentation of similarities and overlaps, which plays an important role in the questioning of categories in queer linguistics. A popular corpus linguistic method that shows a strong orientation towards the detection of differences is keyword analysis (see Baker 2004). It involves the comparison of two corpora at the lexical level and identifies word-forms that occur unusually (in)frequently in a given corpus when compared to a reference corpus (positive and negative keywords), thus overplaying differences between the two corpora. More recent work in LGS studies has taken a critical

stance on research that concentrates exclusively on the documentation of differences, arguing that similarity carries an enormous de-essentialising potential. In tune with this argument, Baker (2011) introduced the notion of a “lockword”, that is, a word whose frequencies are similar across corpora. Another pertinent way to identify similarities between corpora can be to compare three or more datasets, rather than just two (see Baker 2004: 349). For example, instead of exclusively comparing two corpora of gay male and lesbian dating advertisements with each other, one could additionally compare them both to heterosexual advertisements and a general reference corpus (such as BNC or COCA). This procedure will not only show how the gay male and lesbian corpora differ from each other but also what these corpora share.

I close this discussion with a caveat on the practice of establishing differences between corpora through inferential statistics. Once a statistically significant frequency difference is found, it may be treated as a “real” difference. Queer linguists would probably show reservations towards such a mechanistic declaration of differences, echoing a criticism that has previously been voiced, namely that statistically significant differences need not automatically be culturally salient or socially recognised differences (see Cameron 1998b: 41 on statistically based vs. culturally salient keywords). Of course, an identification of differences is not problematic *per se*, and it can easily be reconciled with queer linguistic tenets if it is coupled with a critical analysis of the social effects of the discursive construction of such differences. Much of the corpus linguistic work that we have in language and sexuality studies today operates along these lines. However, there is an additional dimension of difference that may be more relevant to queer linguistic work and has so far played only a minor role in the field. Difference can also be highlighted *within* dominant gender- and sexuality-related categories, and can then be used to challenge hegemonic difference discourses and to show how dominant categories partially overlap, so that a strictly binary conceptualisation becomes suspect.

5. Conclusion

As this overview has shown, the field of LGS studies constitutes a research area that is, methodologically speaking, highly heterogeneous. One reason for this diversity is the fact that gender and sexuality, and their relationships to language, are intrinsically multidimensional and highly complex phenomena whose individual formative aspects necessitate special methodological treatment. While most of the methods identified in this overview are largely restricted to one of the three core areas of LGS studies, corpus linguistics represents a methodology

that can be put to productive use in all three research areas: work on linguistic structures and their usage, sociolinguistic studies and discursive studies on gender and sexuality.

LGS researchers need to critically reflect on the question of which linguistic methods they apply in their studies. Methodological choices will normally be influenced by theoretical considerations, the research object, research questions, data types, and research goals. However, such decisions also require an awareness of the discursive effects of research designs and reflexivity as to whether these effects are compatible with our theoretical convictions and research goals or, less ideally, whether they clash with them. In other words, LGS researchers should be aware of which gender- and sexuality-related discourses they are supporting with the methodological choices they make. This process is not just relevant for the selection of a particular linguistic method but also for the question of how to apply a selected method in a way that is in accordance with the postulated research goals.

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 740257.

Marie Skłodowska-Curie
Actions

References

Adams, Peter J.; Towns, Alison; Gavey, Nicola (1995): Dominance and entitlement. The rhetoric men use to discuss their violence towards women. In: *Discourse & Society* 6 (3), 387–406.

- Bachmann, Ingo (2011): Civil partnership – ‘gay marriage in all but name’: A corpus-driven analysis of discourses of same-sex relationships in the UK Parliament. In: *Corpora* 6 (1), 77–105.
- Baker, Paul (2002): *Polari – The Lost Language of Gay Men*. London: Routledge.
- Baker, Paul (2004): Querying keywords: Questions of difference, frequency, and sense in keywords analysis. In: *Journal of English Linguistics* 32 (4), 346–359.
- Baker, Paul (2005): *Public Discourses of Gay Men*. London: Routledge.
- Baker, Paul (2010): Will Ms ever be as frequent as Mr? A corpus-based comparison of gendered terms across four diachronic corpora of British English. In: *Gender and Language* 4 (1), 125–149.
- Baker, Paul (2013): From gay language to normative discourse. A diachronic corpus analysis of Lavender Linguistics conference abstracts 1994–2012. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 2 (2), 179–205.
- Baker, Paul (2014): ‘Bad wigs and screaming mimis’: Using corpus-assisted techniques to carry out critical discourse analysis of the representation of trans people in the British press. In: Christopher Hart & Piotr Cap (eds.): *Contemporary Critical Discourse Studies*. London: Bloomsbury, 211–235.
- Baker, Paul (2016): Gendered discourses. In: Paul Baker & Jesse Egbert (eds.): *Triangulating Methodological Approaches in Corpus Linguistic Research*. London: Routledge, 138–151.
- Baker, Paul; Egbert, Jesse (eds.) (2016): *Triangulating Methodological Approaches in Corpus Linguistic Research*. London: Routledge.
- Baker, Paul; Levon, Erez (2015): Picking the right cherries? A comparison of corpus-based and qualitative analyses of news articles about masculinity. In: *Discourse & Communication* 9 (2), 221–236.
- Bammesberger, Alfred; Grzegza, Joachim (2001): ModE girl and other terms for ‘young female person’ in English language history. In: *Onomasiology Online* 2, 1–8.
- Barrett, Rusty (2002): Is queer theory important for sociolinguistic theory? In: Kathryn Campbell-Kibler, Robert J. Podesva, Sarah J. Roberts & Andrew Wong (eds.): *Language and Sexuality. Contesting Meaning in Theory and Practice*. Stanford, CA: CSLI, 25–43.
- Barrett, Rusty (2014): The emergence of the unmarked: Queer theory, language ideology, and formal linguistics. In: Lal Zimman, Jenny L. Davis & Joshua

- Raclaw (eds.): *Queer Excursions: Rethorizing Binaries in Language, Gender, and Sexuality*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 195–224.
- Baumgartinger, Persson Perry (2008): Lieb[schtean] Les[schtean], [schtean] du das gerade liest. Von Emanzipation und Pathologisierung, Ermächtigung und Sprachveränderungen. In: *Liminalis* 2, 24–39.
- Baxter, Judith (2002): Competing discourses in the classroom. A post-structuralist discourse analysis of girls' and boys' speech in public contexts. In: *Discourse & Society* 13 (6), 827–842.
- Baxter, Judith (2003): *Positioning Gender in Discourse. A Feminist Methodology*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Bing, Janet M.; Bergvall, Victoria L. (1996): The question of questions. Beyond binary thinking. In: Victoria L. Bergvall, Janet M. Bing & Alice F. Freed (eds.): *Rethinking Language and Gender Research. Theory and Practice*. London: Longman, 1–30.
- Braun, Virginia; Kitzinger, Celia (2001): 'Snatch,' 'hole,' or 'honey-pot'? Semantic categories and the problem of nonspecificity in female genital slang. In: *Journal of Sex Research* 38 (2), 146–158.
- Braun, Friederike; Haig, Geoffrey (2010): When are German 'girls' feminine? How the semantics of age influences the grammar of gender agreement. In: Markus Bieswanger, Heiko Motschenbacher & Susanne Mühleisen (eds.): *Language in its Socio-Cultural Context. New Explorations in Gendered, Global and Media Uses*. Frankfurt am Main: Peter Lang, 69–84.
- Bucholtz, Mary (1999): 'Why be normal'? Language and identity practices in a community of nerd girls. In: *Language in Society* 28 (2), 203–223.
- Bucholtz, Mary (2003): Theories of discourse as theories of gender. Discourse analysis in language and gender studies. In: Janet Holmes & Miriam Meyerhoff (eds.): *The Handbook of Language and Gender*. Oxford: Blackwell, 43–68.
- Butler, Judith (1990): *Gender Trouble. Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*. New York: Routledge.
- Cage, Ken (2003): *Gayle. The Language of Kinks and Queens. A History and Dictionary of Gay Language in South Africa*. Houghton: Jacana Media.
- Cameron, Deborah (1985): *Feminism and Linguistic Theory*. Houndmills: Macmillan.
- Cameron, Deborah (1998a): 'Is there any ketchup, Vera?': Gender, power and pragmatics. In: *Discourse & Society* 9 (4), 437–455.

- Cameron, Deborah (1998b): Dreaming the dictionary: Keywords and corpus linguistics. In: *Key Words: A Journal of Cultural Materialism* 1, 35–46.
- Cameron, Deborah (2005): Relativity and its discontents. Language, gender and pragmatics. In: *Intercultural Pragmatics* 2 (3), 321–334.
- Cameron, Deborah (2011): Sociophonetics and sexuality. Discussion. In: *American Speech* 86 (1), 98–103.
- Carr, Jo; Pauwels, Anne (2006): *Boys and Foreign Language Learning. Real Boys Don't Do Languages*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Chalupnik, Malgorzata; Christie, Christine; Mullany, Louise (2017): (Im)politeness and gender. In: Jonathan Culpeper, Michael Haugh & Dániel Z. Kádár (eds.): *The Palgrave Handbook of Linguistic (Im)politeness*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, 517–537.
- Chirrey, Deborah A. (2003): 'I hereby come out': What sort of speech act is coming out? In: *Journal of Sociolinguistics* 7 (1), 24–37.
- Clark, Kate (1992): The linguistics of blame: Representations of women in The Sun's reporting of crimes of sexual violence. In: Michael Toolan (ed.): *Language, Text and Context: Essays in Stylistics*. London: Routledge: 208–224.
- Coates, Jennifer; Cameron, Deborah (eds.) (1988): *Women in Their Speech Communities. New Perspectives on Language and Sex*. London: Longman.
- Coleman-Fountain, Edmund (2014): Lesbian and gay youth and the question of labels. In: *Sexualities* 17 (7), 802–817.
- Conradie, Marthinus (2011): Constructing femininity. A critical discourse analysis of Cosmo. In: *Southern African Linguistics and Applied Language Studies* 29 (4), 401–417.
- Corbett, Greville G. (2005): Sex-based and non-sex-based gender systems. In: Martin Haspelmath, Matthew S. Dryer, David Gil & Bernard Comrie (eds.): *The World Atlas of Language Structures*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 130–133.
- Corbett, Greville G. (2014): Gender typology. In: Greville G. Corbett (ed.): *The Expression of Gender*. Berlin: Walter der Gruyter, 87–130.
- Decke-Cornill, Helene; Volkmann, Laurenz (eds.) (2007): *Gender Studies and Foreign Language Teaching*. Tübingen: Gunter Narr.
- Doleschal, Ursula (2015): Gender marking. In: Peter O. Müller, Ingeborg Ohnheiser, Susan Olsen & Franz Rainer (eds.): *Word-Formation: An International Handbook of the Languages of Europe*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton, 1159–1171.

- Eckert, Penelope (1989): The whole woman. Sex and gender differences in variation. In: *Language Variation and Change* 1 (3), 245–267.
- Eckert, Penelope; McConnell-Ginet, Sally (1992): Think practically and look locally. Language and gender as community-based practice. In: *Annual Review of Anthropology* 21, 461–490.
- Edley, Nigel; Wetherell, Margaret (2008): Discursive Psychology and the study of gender. A contested space. In: Kate Harrington, Lia Litosseliti, Helen Sauntson & Jane Sunderland (eds.): *Gender and Language Research Methodologies*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 161–173.
- Ehrlich, Susan (2001): *Representing Rape. Language and Sexual Consent*. London: Routledge.
- Fishman, Pamela M. (1978): Interaction. The work women do. In: *Social Problems* 25, 397–406.
- Frank, Roberta (2003): Sex in the Dictionary of Old English. In: Mark C. Amodio & O'Brien O'Keeffe, Katherine (eds.): *Unlocking the Wordhord. Anglo-Saxon Studies in Memory of Edward B. Irving, Jr.* Toronto: University of Toronto, 302–312.
- Gardelle, Laure (2015): Sex-indefinite references to human beings in American English. In: Laure Gardelle & Sandrine Sorlin (eds.): *The Pragmatics of Personal Pronouns*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 69–92.
- George, Gloria (1999): Sexual orientation and the Oxford Dictionary of Slang. In: *English Today* 15 (3), 52–57.
- Gleason, Jean Berko; Ely, Richard (2002): Gender differences in language development. In: Ann McGillicuddy-De Lisi & De Lisi, Richard (eds.): *Biology, Society, and Behavior. The Development of Sex Differences in Cognition*. Westport, CT: Ablex, 127–154.
- Grimm, Anne (2008): 'Männersprache' - 'Frauensprache'? Eine korpusgestützte empirische Analyse des Sprachgebrauchs britischer und amerikanischer Frauen und Männer hinsichtlich Geschlechtsspezifika. Hamburg: Dr. Kovac.
- Hall, Kira (2013): 'It's a hijra!'. Queer linguistics revisited. In: *Discourse & Society* 24 (5), 634–642.
- Hall, Matthew; Gough, Brendan; Seymour-Smith, Sarah; Hansen, Susan (2012): On-line constructions of metrosexuality and masculinities. A membership categorization analysis. In: *Gender and Language* 6 (2), 379–403.

Harrington, Kate; Litosseliti, Lia; Sauntson, Helen; Sunderland, Jane (eds.) (2008): *Gender and Language Research Methodologies*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.

Harting, Axel (2005): Pragmatic idioms in Australian English. A survey of gender and age-related usage of greetings, leave-takings, thanks, and apologies. In: *Studies in Language and Literature* 24 (2), 53–79.

Harvey, Keith (1997): ‘Everybody loves a lover’: Gay men, straight men and a problem of lexical choice. In: Keith Harvey & Celia Shalom (eds.): *Language and Desire: Encoding Sex, Romance and Intimacy*. London: Routledge: 60–82.

Harvey, Keith (2002): Camp talk and citationality. A queer take on ‘authentic’ and ‘represented’ utterance. In: *Journal of Pragmatics* 34 (9), 1145–1165.

Heisterkamp, Brian L. (2016): Challenging heteronormativity: Recontextualizing references to members of gay male and lesbian couples. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 5 (1), 37–60.

Hellinger, Marlis; Bußmann, Hadumod (2001): Gender across languages. The linguistic representation of women and men. In: Marlis Hellinger & Hadumod Bußmann (eds.): *Gender Across Languages. The Linguistic Representation of Women and Men. Volume I*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 1–25.

Hellinger, Marlis; Bußmann, Hadumod (eds.) (2001–2003): *Gender Across Languages. The Linguistic Representation of Women and Men. Volumes I–III*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.

Hellinger, Marlis; Motschenbacher, Heiko (eds.) (2015): *Gender Across Languages. The Linguistic Representation of Women and Men. Volume 4*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.

Hidalgo Tenorio, Encarnación (2000): Gender, sex and stereotyping in the Collins COBUILD English Language Dictionary. In: *Australian Journal of Linguistics* 20 (2), 211–230.

Hiramoto, Mie; Teo, Cherise Shi Ling (2015): Heteronormative love makes a house a home: Multimodal analysis of luxury housing ads in Singapore. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 4 (2), 223–253.

Holmes, Janet (1995): *Women, Men and Politeness*. London: Longman.

Holmes, Janet; Meyerhoff, Miriam (1999): The community of practice. Theories and methodologies in language and gender research. In: *Language in Society* 28 (2), 173–183.

- Holmes-Elliott, Sophie (2016): Ladies first? Adolescent peaks in a male-led change. In: *University of Pennsylvania Working Papers in Linguistics* 22 (2), 81–90.
- Hultgren, Anna Kristina (2008): Reconstructing the sex dichotomy in language and gender research. Some advantages of using correlational sociolinguistics. In: Kate Harrington, Lia Litosseliti, Helen Sauntson & Jane Sunderland (eds.): *Gender and Language Research Methodologies*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 29–42.
- Hunt, Sally (2015): ‘Mother of the nation’: Representations of womanhood in the South African media. In: Mirjana N. Dedaić (eds.): *Singing, Speaking and Writing Politics: South African Political Discourses*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 169–199.
- Jäkel, Olaf (2014): Denotational boundary disputes in political discourse: ‘Defining the definition of marriage’. In: *Journal of Language and Politics* 13 (2), 336–363.
- Jaworska, Sylvia; Krishnamurthy, Ramesh (2012): On the F word. A corpus-based analysis of the media representation of feminism in British and German press discourse, 1990–2009. In: *Discourse & Society* 23 (4), 401–431.
- Jaworski, Adam (1986): *A Linguistic Picture of Women’s Position in Society. A Polish-English Contrastive Study*. Frankfurt: Peter Lang.
- Jefferson, Gail (2004): Glossary of transcript symbols with an introduction. In: Lerner, Gene H. (ed.): *Conversation Analysis. Studies from the First Generation*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 13–31.
- Jiménez Catalán, Rosa María (ed.) (2010): *Gender Perspectives on Vocabulary in Foreign and Second Languages*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Johnson, Alison J. (2018): ‘How came you not to cry out?’: Pragmatic effects of negative questioning in child rape trials in the Old Bailey Proceedings 1730–1798. In: Dennis Kurzon & Barbara Kryk-Kastovsky (eds.): *Legal Pragmatics*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 41–64.
- Jones, Lucy (2012): *Dyke/Girl. Language and Identities in a Lesbian Group*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Jones, Lucy (2014): ‘Dolls or teddies?’: Constructing lesbian identity through community-specific practice. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 3 (2), 161–190.
- Jones, Lucy; Mills, Sara; Paterson, Laura L.; Turner, Georgina; Coffey-Glover, Laura (2017): Identity and naming practices in British marriage and civil partnerships. In: *Gender and Language* 11 (3), 309–335.

Jung, Woo-Hyun (1997): Contrastive analysis of lexical items involving sexism in English and Korean. In: *Papers and Studies in Contrastive Linguistics* 32, 57–64.

Khan, Manizeh; Daneman, Meredyth (2011): How readers spontaneously interpret man-suffix words. Evidence from eye movements. In: *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research* 40 (5/6), 351–366.

Kiesling, Scott Fabius (2005): Homosocial desire in men's talk. Balancing and re-creating cultural discourses of masculinity. In: *Language in Society* 34 (5), 695–726.

King, Brian W. (2011): Language, sexuality and place. The view from cyberspace. In: *Gender and Language* 5 (1), 1–30.

Kitzinger, Celia (2000): Doing feminist conversation analysis. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 10 (2), 163–193.

Kitzinger, Celia (2005): 'Speaking as a heterosexual': (How) Does sexuality matter for talk-in-interaction? In: *Research on Language and Social Interaction* 38 (3), 221–265.

Kitzinger, Celia (2007): Is 'woman' always relevantly gendered? In: *Gender and Language* 1 (1), 39–49.

Kitzinger, Celia (2008): Conversation Analysis. Technical matters for gender research. In: Kate Harrington, Lia Litosseliti, Helen Sauntson & Jane Sunderland (eds.): *Gender and Language Research Methodologies*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 119–138.

Kitzinger, Celia; Wilkinson, Sue (2017): Referring to persons: Linguistic gender and gender in action – (when) are husbands men? In: Emanuel A. Schegloff, Geoffrey Raymond, Lerner, Gene H. & John Heritage (eds.): *Enabling Human Conduct: Studies of Talk-in-Interaction in Honor of Emanuel A. Schegloff*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 189–204.

Kleparski, Grzegorz A. (2004): CDs, petticoats, skirts, ankas, tamaras and sheilas. The metonymical rise of lexical categories related to the conceptual category FEMALE HUMAN BEING. In: Christian J. Kay & Smith, Jeremy J. (eds.): *Categorization in the History of English*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 71–84.

Kochman-Haladyj, Bozena; Kleparski, Grzegorz A. (2011): On Pejorisation of Women Terms in the History of English. Rzeszów: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Rzeszowskiego.

Koller, Veronika (2011): Analysing lesbian identity in discourse. Combining discourse-historical and socio-cognitive approaches. In: Christopher Hart (ed.):

Critical Discourse Studies in Context and Cognition. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 119–142.

Koller, Veronika (2015): The subversive potential of queer pornography: A systemic-functional analysis of a written online text. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 4 (2), 254–271.

König, Ekkehard; Gast, Volker (2009): Understanding English-German Contrasts. Berlin: Erich Schmidt.

Kornexl, Lucia (2008): Women and other ‘small things’: *-ette* as a feminine marker. In: Richard Dury, Maurizio Gotti & Marina Dossena (eds.): *English Historical Linguistics 2006. Volume II. Lexical and Semantic Change*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 241–257.

Korobov, Neill (2001): Reconciling theory with method: From conversation analysis and critical discourse analysis to positioning analysis. In: *Forum: Qualitative Social Research* 2 (3), Art.11 [1-19].

Korobov, Neill (2013): Positioning identities. A discursive approach to the negotiation of gendered categories. In: *Narrative Inquiry* 23 (1), 111–131.

Kremer, Marion (1997): Person Reference and Gender in Translation. A Contrastive Investigation of English and German. Tübingen: Gunter Narr.

Kulick, Don (1999): Transgender and language. A review of the literature and suggestions for the future. In: *GLQ* 5 (4), 605–622.

Kulick, Don (2000): Gay and lesbian language. In: *Annual Review of Anthropology* 29, 243–285.

Kulick, Don (2005): The importance of what gets left out. In: *Discourse Studies* 7 (4/5), 615–624.

Labov, William (1990): The intersection of sex and social class in the course of linguistic change. In: *Language Variation and Change* 2 (2), 205–254.

Lakoff, Robin (1975): *Language and Woman’s Place*. New York: Harper & Row.

Land, Victoria; Kitzinger, Celia (2005): Speaking as a lesbian. Correcting the heterosexist presumption. In: *Research on Language and Social Interaction* 38 (4), 371–416.

Lange, Benjamin P.; Euler, Harald A.; Zaretsky, Eugen (2016): Sex differences in language competence of 3- to 6-year-old children. In: *Applied Psycholinguistics* 37 (6), 1417–1438.

- Lawson, Robert (2011): Patterns of linguistic variation among Glaswegian adolescent males. In: *Journal of Sociolinguistics* 15 (2), 226–255.
- Lazar, Michelle M. (2018): Feminist critical discourse analysis. In: John Flowerdew & John E. Richardson (eds.): *The Routledge Handbook of Critical Discourse Studies*. Oxford: Routledge, 372–387.
- Leap, William L. (ed.) (1995): *Beyond the Lavender Lexicon. Authenticity, Imagination, and Appropriation in Lesbian and Gay Languages*. Luxembourg: Gordon and Breach.
- Leap, William L. (2002): Studying lesbian and gay languages. Vocabulary, text-making, and beyond. In: Ellen Lewin & William L. Leap (eds.): *Out in Theory. The Emergence of Lesbian and Gay Anthropology*. Urbana: University of Illinois, 128–154.
- Leap, William L. (2015): Queer linguistics as critical discourse analysis. In: Deborah Tannen, Heidi E. Hamilton & Deborah Schiffrin (eds.): *The Handbook of Discourse Analysis*. Second edition. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 661–680.
- Levon, Erez (2011): Teasing apart to bring together. Gender and sexuality in variationist research. In: *American Speech* 86 (1), 69–84.
- Liddicoat, Anthony (2007): *An Introduction to Conversation Analysis*. London: Continuum.
- Lillian, Donna L. (2007): A thorn by any other name. Sexist discourse as hate speech. In: *Discourse & Society* 18 (6), 719–740.
- Litosseliti, Lia (2003): *Using Focus Groups in Research*. London: Continuum.
- Love, Robbie; Baker, Paul (2015): The hate that dare not speak its name? In: *Journal of Language Aggression and Conflict* 3 (1), 57–86.
- Luchjenbroers, June; Aldridge-Waddon, Michelle (2011): Paedophiles and politeness in email communications. Community of practice needs that define face-threat. In: *Journal of Politeness Research* 7 (1), 21–42.
- Machin, David; Caldas-Coulthard, Carmen Rosa; Milani, Tommaso M. (2016): Doing critical multimodality in research on gender, language and discourse. In: *Gender and Language* 10 (3), 301–308.
- Machin, David; Mayr, Andrea (2012): *How to Do Critical Discourse Analysis*. London: Sage.
- Makoni, Busi (2016): Labelling black male genitalia and the ‘new racism’: The discursive construction of sexual racism by a group of Southern African college students. In: *Gender and Language* 10 (1), 48–72.

- Manning, Elizabeth (1997): Kissing and cuddling: The reciprocity of romantic and sexual activity. In: Keith Harvey & Celia Shalom (eds.): *Language and Desire: Encoding Sex, Romance and Intimacy*. London: Routledge: 43–59.
- McEnery, Tony; Hardie, Andrew (2012): *Corpus Linguistics: Method, Theory and Practice*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Milani, Tommaso M. (2013): Expanding the Queer Linguistic scene. Multimodality, space and sexuality at a South African university. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 2 (2), 206–234.
- Miller, Megan M.; James, Lori E. (2009): Is the generic pronoun he still comprehended as excluding women? In: *American Journal of Psychology* 122 (4), 483–496.
- Mills, Jane (1989): *Womanwords. A Vocabulary of Culture and Patriarchal Society*. Harlow: Longman.
- Mills, Sara (2003): *Gender and Politeness*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mills, Sara (2008): *Language and Sexism*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mills, Sara (2012): *Gender Matters. Feminist Linguistic Analysis*. London: Equinox.
- Morin, Regina (2010): Terminal letters, phonemes, and morphemes in Spanish gender assignment. In: *Linguistics* 48 (1), 143–169.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2007): Can the term ‘genderlect’ be saved? A postmodernist re-definition. In: *Gender and Language* 1 (2), 255–278.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2009): Speaking the gendered body. The performative construction of commercial femininities and masculinities via body-part vocabulary. In: *Language in Society* 38 (1), 1–22.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2010): *Language, Gender and Sexual Identity. Poststructuralist Perspectives*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2011): Taking Queer Linguistics further. Sociolinguistics and critical heteronormativity research. In: *International Journal of the Sociology of Language* 212, 149–179.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2012a): *An Interdisciplinary Bibliography on Language, Gender and Sexuality (2000-2011)*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.

- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2012b): 'I think Houston wants a kiss right?'. Linguistic constructions of heterosexualities at Eurovision Song Contest press conferences. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 1 (2), 127–150.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2013): Gentlemen before ladies? A corpus-based study of conjunct order in personal binomials. In: *Journal of English Linguistics* 41 (3), 212–242.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2014a): Grammatical gender as a challenge for language policy: The (im)possibility of non-heteronormative language use in German versus English. In: *Language Policy* 13 (3), 243–261.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2014b): Focusing on normativity in language and sexuality studies. Insights from conversations on objectophilia. In: *Critical Discourse Studies* 11 (1), 49–70.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2015): Some new perspectives on gendered language structures. In: Marlis Hellinger & Heiko Motschenbacher (eds.): *Gender Across Languages. The Linguistic Representation of Women and Men. Volume 4*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 27–48.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2016a): Gender, inclusion and English language teaching: A linguistic perspective. In: Daniela Elsner & Viviane Lohe (eds.): *Gender and Language Learning: Research and Practice*. Tübingen: Narr, 97–112.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2016b): A discursive approach to structural gender linguistics: Theoretical and methodological considerations. In: *Gender and Language* 10 (2), 149–169.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2017): Compliments, gender and sexuality in European ELF talk. In: Peter Handler, Klaus Kaindl & Holger Wochele (eds.): *Ceci n'est pas une festschrift: Texte zur Angewandten und Romanistischen Sprachwissenschaft für Martin Stegu*. Berlin: Logos, 259–278.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (ed.) (2018a): *Corpus Linguistics in Language and Sexuality Studies* (special issue: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 8.2). Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2018b): Corpus linguistics in language and sexuality studies: Taking stock and future directions. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 8 (2), 145–174.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (2018c): Sexuality in critical discourse studies. In: John Flowerdew & John E. Richardson (eds.): *The Routledge Handbook of Critical Discourse Studies*. Oxford: Routledge, 388–402.

- Motschenbacher, Heiko (forthcoming a): Language and sexual normativity. In: Rusty Barrett & Kira Hall (eds.): *The Oxford Handbook of Language and Sexuality*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (forthcoming b): Sexuality and linguistic inclusion: An analysis of the German EFL textbook series Navi. In: Łukasz Pakuła (ed.): *Linguistic Perspectives on Sexuality in Education*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko (forthcoming c): *Gay people and homosexual persons: A co-occurrence analysis of the usage patterns of adjectival sexual descriptors in COCA*.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko & Roivainen, Eka (forthcoming): A corpus-based comparison of adjectival collocates of person, woman and man. *Journal of Language and Discrimination*.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko; Stegu, Martin (2013): Queer Linguistic approaches to discourse. In: *Discourse & Society* 24 (5), 519–535.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko; Stegu, Martin (eds.) (2013): Queer Linguistic Approaches to Discourse (special issue: *Discourse & Society* 24.5). Los Angeles: Sage.
- Motschenbacher, Heiko; Weikert, Marija (2015): Structural gender trouble in Croatian. In: Marlis Hellinger & Heiko Motschenbacher (eds.): *Gender Across Languages. The Linguistic Representation of Women and Men. Volume 4*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 49–95.
- Munson, Benjamin; Ryherd, Kayleigh; Kemper, Sara (2017): Implicit and explicit gender priming in English lingual sibilant fricative perception. In: *Linguistics* 55 (5), 1073–1107.
- Musgrave, Kate (1992): Eve names names. Feminist neology and how to do it. In: *Women and Language* 15 (1), 27–31.
- Naseem, M. Ayaz (2006): The soldier and the seductress. A post-structuralist analysis of gendered citizenship through inclusion in and exclusion from language and social studies textbooks in Pakistan. In: *International Journal of Inclusive Education* 10 (4/5), 449–467.
- Nevala, Minna; Hintikka, Marianna (2009): Cider-wenches and high prized pin-boxes: Bawdy terminology in seventeenth- and eighteenth-century England. In: Roderick W. McConchie, Alpo Honkapohja & Jukka Tyrkkö (eds.): *Selected Proceedings of the 2008 Symposium on New Approaches in English Historical Lexis (HEL-LEX 2)*. Somerville, MA: Cascadilla Proceedings Project: 134–152.

- Norri, Juhani (1997): Lexical gender-benders in underwear. In: Yvonne Hyrynen (ed.): *Voicing Gender*. Tampere: University of Tampere, 63–101.
- Ogiermann, Eva (2008): On the culture-specificity of linguistic gender differences. The case of English and Russian apologies. In: *Intercultural Pragmatics* 5 (3), 259–286.
- Ostermann, Ana Cristina (2003): Communities of practice at work. Gender, facework and the power of habitus at an all-female police station and a feminist crisis intervention center in Brazil. In: *Discourse & Society* 14 (4), 473–505.
- Page, Ruth E. (2003): An analysis of APPRAISAL in childbirth narratives with special consideration of gender and storytelling style. In: *Text* 23 (2), 211–237.
- Partington, Alan (2014): Mind the gaps: The role of corpus linguistics in researching absences. In: *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics* 19 (1), 118–146.
- Paterson, Laura Louise (2014): *British Pronoun Use, Prescription, and Processing: Linguistic and Social Influences Affecting ‘They’ and ‘He’*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Pauwels, Anne (2011): Planning for a global lingua franca. Challenges for feminist language planning in English(es) around the world. In: *Current Issues in Language Planning* 12 (1), 9–19.
- Peitsara, Kirsti (2006): MAN-Compounds in English. In: R. W. McConchie, Olga Timofeeva, Heli Tissari & Tanja Säily (eds.): *Selected Proceedings of the 2005 Symposium on New Approaches in English Historical Lexis (HEL-LEX)*. Somerville, MA: Cascadia Proceedings Project, 113–122.
- Persson, Gunnar; Rydén, Mats (1995): The project "Male and Female Terms in English". A diachronic study of a semantic field. In: Henryk Kardela & Gunnar Persson (eds.): *New Trends in Semantics and Lexicography. Proceedings of the International Conference at Kazimierz, December 13-15, 1993*. Umea: Swedish Science, 145–150.
- Persson, Gunnar; Rydén, Mats (eds.) (1996): *Male and Female Terms in English. Proceedings of the Symposium at Umea University, May 18-19, 1994*. Umea: Umea University.
- Peterson, David (2011): Neoliberal homophobic discourse. Heteronormative human capital and the exclusion of queer citizens. In: *Journal of Homosexuality* 58 (6/7), 742–757.
- Pidwell, Ruth (1998): Difference revisited. Women, men, and religious discourse. In: *Social Semiotics* 8 (1), 71–92.

- Podesva, Robert J.; Eckert, Penelope (eds.) (2011): Sociophonetics and Sexuality (special issue: *American Speech* 86.1). Durham, NC: Duke University Press.
- Podesva, Robert J.; Kajino, Sakiko (2014): Sociophonetics, gender, and sexuality. In: Susan Ehrlich, Miriam Meyerhoff & Janet Holmes (eds.): *The Handbook of Language, Gender, and Sexuality*. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 103–122.
- Posch, Claudia (2009): *Feminist Linguistics and Corpus Linguistics: A Database of Genderfair Language Use with Non-Human Referents*. Munich: GRIN.
- Rayson, Paul; Leech, Geoffrey; Hodges, Mary (1997): Social differentiation in the use of English vocabulary. Some analyses of the conversational component of the British National Corpus. In: *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics* 2 (1), 133–152.
- Russell, Eric Louis (2017): Style shifting and the phonetic performance of gay vs. straight: A case study from French. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 6 (1), 128–176.
- Sandfield, Anna; Percy, Carol (2003): Accounting for single status. Heterosexism and ageism in heterosexual women's talk about marriage. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 13 (4), 475–488.
- Sauntson, Helen (2007): Education, culture and the construction of sexual identity. An APPRAISAL analysis of lesbian coming out narratives. In: Helen Sauntson & Sakis Kyratzis (eds.): *Language, Sexualities and Desires. Cross-Cultural Perspectives*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 140–164.
- Sauntson, Helen (2012): *Approaches to Gender and Spoken Classroom Discourse*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Sauntson, Helen (2015): Sexualities equality and diversity training in UK schools: An appraisal analysis of teachers' reflections, attitudes and experiences. In: Allyson Jule (ed.): *Shifting Visions: Gender and Discourses*. Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 168–190.
- Sauntson, Helen; Simpson, Kathryn (2011): Investigating sexuality discourses in the U.K. secondary English curriculum. In: *Journal of Homosexuality* 58 (6/7), 953–973.
- Sauntson, Helen; Sundaram, Vanita (2016): Discursive silences: Critically analysing the presence/absence of sexual diversity in the sex and relationships education guidance for England and Wales. In: Vanita Sundaram & Helen Sauntson (eds.): *Global Perspectives and Key Debates in Sex and Relationships Education: Addressing Issues of Gender, Sexuality, Plurality and Power*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 100–114.

- Scheller-Boltz, Dennis (2017): Challenging genderless masculinity: Gender agreement in Russian interrogative sentences with *kto*. In: *Studia Slavica* 21 (1), 137–151.
- Schmid, Hans-Jörg (2003): Do women and men really live in different cultures? Evidence from the BNC. In: Andrew Wilson, Paul Rayson & Tony McEnery (eds.): *Corpus Linguistics by the Lune. A Festschrift for Geoffrey Leech*. Frankfurt: Peter Lang, 185–221.
- Schmid, Hans-Jörg (2015): Does gender-related variation still have an effect, even when topic and (almost) everything else is controlled? In: Jocelyne Daems, Eline Zenner, Kris Heylen, Dirk Speelman & Hubert Cuyckens (eds.): *Change of Paradigms – New Paradoxes: Recontextualizing Language and Linguistics*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton, 327–346.
- Schneider, Britta (2013a): Heteronormativity and queerness in transnational heterosexual Salsa communities. In: *Discourse & Society* 24 (5), 553–571.
- Schneider, Britta (2013b): ‘In Salsa, it’s okay to be a woman’: Legitimizing heteronormativity in a culturally ‘other’ environment. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 2 (2), 262–291.
- Schröter, Melani; Taylor, Charlotte (eds.) (2018): *Exploring Silence and Absence in Discourse: Empirical Approaches*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Siewierska, Anna (2005): Gender distinctions in independent personal pronouns. In: Martin Haspelmath, Matthew S. Dryer, David Gil & Bernard Comrie (eds.): *The World Atlas of Language Structures*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 182–185.
- Sokalska-Bennett, Aleksandra (2017): ‘Imagine a boy who is adopted by a pair of lesbians (poor little sod)...’: A membership categorisation analysis of online comments on same-gender adoption. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 6 (1), 61–89.
- Speer, Susan A. (2005): *Gender Talk. Feminism, Discourse and Conversation Analysis*. London: Routledge.
- Speer, Susan A.; Potter, Jonathan (2002): From performatives to practices. Judith Butler, discursive psychology and the management of heterosexist talk. In: Paul McIlvenny (ed.): *Talking Gender and Sexuality*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 151–180.
- Speer, Susan A.; Stokoe, Elizabeth (eds.) (2011): *Conversation and Gender*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Stockill, Clare; Kitzinger, Celia (2007): Gendered ‘people’: How linguistically non-gendered terms can have gendered interactional relevance. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 17 (2), 224–236.
- Stokoe, Elizabeth (2008): Categories, actions and sequences. Formulating gender in talk-in-interaction. In: Kate Harrington, Lia Litosseliti, Helen Sauntson & Jane Sunderland (eds.): *Gender and Language Research Methodologies*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 139–157.
- Stokoe, Elizabeth (2010): ‘I’m not gonna hit a lady’: Conversation analysis, membership categorization and men’s denials of violence towards women. In: *Discourse & Society* 21 (1), 59–82.
- Stokoe, Elizabeth (2012): Moving forward with membership categorization analysis. Methods for systematic analysis. In: *Discourse Studies* 14 (3), 277–303.
- Sunderland, Jane (2004): *Gendered Discourses*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Sunderland, Jane (2015): Gender (representation) in foreign language textbooks: Avoiding pitfalls and moving on. In: Abolaji S. Mustapha & Sara Mills (eds.): *Gender Representation in Learning Materials: International Perspectives*. London: Routledge, 19–34.
- Sunderland, Jane; Litosseliti, Lia (2002): Gender identity and discourse analysis. Theoretical and empirical considerations. In: Lia Litosseliti & Jane Sunderland (eds.): *Gender Identity and Discourse Analysis*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 3–39.
- Sunderland, Jane; McGlashan, Mark (2012): The linguistic, visual and multimodal representation of two-Mum and two-Dad families in children’s picturebooks. In: *Language & Literature* 21 (2), 189–210.
- Takahashi, Kimie (2013): *Language Learning, Gender and Desire: Japanese Women on the Move*. Bristol: Multilingual Matters.
- Taylor, Charlotte (2013): Searching for similarity using corpus-assisted discourse studies. In: *Corpora* 8 (1), 81–113.
- Thurlow, Crispin (2001): Naming the ‘outsider within’: Homophobic pejoratives and the verbal abuse of lesbian, gay and bisexual high-school pupils. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 24 (1), 25–38.
- Tissari, Heli (2005): LOVE in words. Experience and conceptualization in the modern English lexicon of LOVE. In: Nicole Delbecque, van der Auwera, Johan & Dirk Geeraerts (eds.): *Perspectives on Variation. Sociolinguistic, Historical, Comparative*. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter, 143–176.

- Trudgill, Peter (1972): Sex, covert prestige and linguistic change in the urban British English of Norwich. In: *Language in Society* 1 (2), 179–195.
- Turowetz, Jason; Hollander, Matthew M. (2012): Assessing the experience of speed dating. In: *Discourse Studies* 14 (5), 635–658.
- Velupillai, Viveka (2012): *An Introduction to Linguistic Typology*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Watson, Greg (2012): Pragmatic acts of love. In: *Language & Literature* 21 (2), 150–169.
- Weatherall, Ann; Stubbe, Maria; Sunderland, Jane; Baxter, Judith (2010): Conversation analysis and critical discourse analysis in language and gender research. Approaches in dialogue. In: Janet Holmes & Meredith Marra (eds.): *Femininity, Feminism and Gendered Discourse. A Selected and Edited Collection of Papers from the Fifth International Language and Gender Association Conference (IGALA5)*. Newcastle upon Tyne: Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 213–243.
- Wetherell, Margaret (1998): Positioning and interpretative repertoires. Conversation Analysis and post-structuralism in dialogue. In: *Discourse & Society* 9 (3), 387–412.
- Wilkinson, Sue; Kitzinger, Celia (2014): Conversation analysis in language and gender studies. In: Susan Ehrlich, Miriam Meyerhoff & Janet Holmes (eds.): *The Handbook of Language, Gender, and Sexuality*. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 141–160.
- Winter, Jo; Pauwels, Anne (2006): Men staying at home looking after their children. Feminist linguistic reform and social change. In: *International Journal of Applied Linguistics* 16 (1), 16–36.
- Wodak, Ruth (2005): Gender mainstreaming and the European Union. Interdisciplinarity, gender studies and CDA. In: Michelle M. Lazar (ed.): *Feminist Critical Discourse Analysis. Gender, Power and Ideology in Discourse*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 90–113.
- Wodak, Ruth (2008): Controversial issues in Feminist Critical Discourse Analysis. In: Kate Harrington, Lia Litosseliti, Helen Sauntson & Jane Sunderland (eds.): *Gender and Language Research Methodologies*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 193–210.
- Wodak, Ruth; Meyer, Michael (eds.) (2016): *Methods of Critical Discourse Studies*. 3rd ed. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Wolfson, Nessa (1984): Pretty is as pretty does. A speech act view of sex roles. In: *Applied Linguistics* 5 (3), 236–244.

Yang, Xueyan (2017): Father identities constructed through meaning choices: A systemic-functional analysis of fathers' letters in *Dad Where Are We Going*. In: *Text & Talk* 37 (3), 359–386.

Zimman, Lal (2013): Hegemonic masculinity and the variability of gay-sounding speech. The perceived sexuality of transgender men. In: *Journal of Language and Sexuality* 2 (1), 1–39.

Zimman, Lal (2014): The discursive construction of sex: Remaking and reclaiming the gendered body in talk about genitals among trans men. In: Lal Zimman, Jenny L. Davis & Joshua Raclaw (eds.): *Queer Excursions: Rethorizing Binaries in Language, Gender, and Sexuality*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 13–34.

Zimman, Lal; Davis, Jenny L.; Raclaw, Joshua (eds.) (2014): *Queer Excursions: Rethorizing Binaries in Language, Gender, and Sexuality*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Zimman, Lal; Hall, Kira (2016): *Oxford Bibliographies: Language, Gender, and Sexuality*. <http://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/view/document/obo-9780199772810/obo-9780199772810-0109.xml> (last accessed: 05 May 2018).